

EXPERIMENTAL INVESTIGATION OF REINFORCED FLAT SLABS WITH TRUSS-SHAPED PUNCHING SHEAR REINFORCEMENT

Shamshinar Salehuddin^{1,2}, Shaharudin Shah Zaini^{1*}, Megat Azmi Megat Johari¹, Ahmad Nurfaidhi Rizalman³, Nur Liza Rahim² & Mustaqqim Abdul Rahim²

¹School of Civil Engineering, Universiti Sains Malaysia, 14300 Nibong Tebal, Pulau Pinang, Malaysia

²Department of Civil Engineering, Faculty of Civil Engineering Technology, Universiti Malaysia Perlis, 02600, Arau, Perlis, Malaysia

³Faculty of Engineering, Universiti Malaysia Sabah

ABSTRACT

This research is conducted with the aim to evaluate the effectiveness of a simple and cost-effective truss-shaped punching shear reinforcement that was placed in a 1200 mm × 1200 mm × 175 mm thick flat slab specimen. Three types of truss-shaped were proposed namely plain box (Type 1), box with vertical and inclined internal members (Type 2), and box with inclined internal members only (Type 3). The experimental results showed that the average punching shear capacity were recorded to be 140.026 kN, 150.818 kN, 161.430 kN and 170.089 kN for Control, FS1, FS2 and FS3 specimens, respectively. As such, the use of truss-shaped punching shear reinforcement increased the punching shear capacity up to 21.47 %. The enhancement of punching shear capacity showed by FS3 can be associated to the presence of inclined members that are capable to intercept more shear cracks.

INTRODUCTION

Typically, in a building, the load from the slab is supported by beam that in turn, is transferred to the respective column. This type of structural assembly is known as the slab-beam systems (Alwash and Al-Mamoori, 2018). However, there is another type of slab construction that is independent on beam as a support where the load from the slab can be safely and directly transferred to column. This type of assembly is termed as flat slab and generally can be seen in the construction of warehouse, parking space in a building, and public hall.

The critical considerations in the design of flat slab is the punching shear force within the vicinity the column (Girish and Lingeshwaran, 2018). At slab-column connection, shear force and moment in the flat slab are transferred to the supporting column by shear stress acting on the portion of slab close to column face. The tensile stress induced by this shear stress contributes to the formation of inclined cracks that propagates around the column. Consequently, an inverted truncated cone surface is generated around the column as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1 Punching failure in the slab-column connection area (Saadoon et al., 2019)

One of the factors that affect punching shear capacity is by adding punching shear reinforcement in the design of flat slab. There are many types of punching shear reinforcement proposed by several researchers. Caldentey et al. (2013) studied the influence of closed stirrups on the punching shear strength of concrete flat slab. The authors reported that adding closed stirrups without engaging the tensile longitudinal reinforcement improved the punching shear capacity of the slabs by 24.6 % compared to the control specimen (without punching shear reinforcement). Likewise, Mabrouk et al. (2017) performed the experimental investigation on the effect of closed stirrups on the punching shear capacity of flat slab. In general, the results showed that the enhancement to the punching shear capacity were in the range of 22.6 % to 43.1 %. Bartolac et al. (2015) investigated the performance of a z-shaped shear reinforcement in flat slab to resist punching shear force. The authors reported that the flat slab strengthened with z-shaped shear reinforcement exhibited punching shear capacity that was approximately 17 % greater than the slab without shear reinforcement. Moreover, Pilakoutas and Li (2003) conducted an experimental to investigate the effectiveness of shearband system. In their study, the punching shear capacity was reported to increase approximately 23.3 % compared to the control specimen.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

Specimen Details

In the experimental work, the size of flat slab specimens used was 1200 mm × 1200 mm × 175 mm thick embedded with BRC A8 (steel mesh) as the flexural reinforcement. A column stub 200 × 200 × 150 mm thick was placed at the centre of the flat slab. Flat Slab 1 (FS1) with punching shear reinforcement Type 1 (plain box), Flat Slab 2 (FS2) with punching shear reinforcement Type 2 (box with vertical and inclined internal members) and Flat Slab 3 (FS3) with punching shear reinforcement Type 3 (box with inclined internal members only) were developed as shown in Figure 2. The concrete strength was set at 26 N/mm² based on cube compression strength.

Figure 2 Arrangement of steel reinforcement for (a) Control, (b) FS1, (c) FS2 and (d) FS3

The study was extended to determine the stiffness, ductility ratio and absorption energy from the load-deflection curve plotted from experimental work. The stiffness was calculated using equation 3.1. In this case, the yield point on the curve was defined as the end of the linear phase before arriving into the non-linear phase (Husain et al., 2017).

$$K_s = \frac{P_y}{\Delta_y} \quad \text{Equation 3.1}$$

where;

K_s = Secant stiffness (kN/mm)
 P_y = Load at yield point (kN)
 Δ_y = Yield deflection (mm)

The ductility ratio is defined as the ratio of the deflection at failure or at ultimate load (Δ_u) to the deflection at first yielding of the specimen (Δ_y) as stated by Nayef et al. (2019). The equation to calculate the ductility is as follows: -

$$\mu_d = \frac{\Delta_u}{\Delta_y} \quad \text{Equation 3.2}$$

On the other hand, the energy absorption was determined by calculating the area under the load-deflection curve. The area under the curve was considered from the origin up to the failure point as recommended by Ahmed et al. (2018). Al-Salim et al. (2021) also stated that the measurement of energy absorption capacity up to the failure point is the most appropriate approach in determining part of the structural behaviour. The energy absorption capacity was obtained by integrating the polynomial equation.

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

Load-Deflection Curve

Figure 3 (a), (b), (c) and (d) show the load-deflection curve for each type of flat slab specimen. The load-deflection development, measured by 1 LVDT placed on the top surface of the column on centre for each specimen. In general, all graphs show similar load-deflection pattern. The average maximum deflection for Control, FS1, FS2 and FS3 was recorded to be 17.648 mm, 20.108 mm, 20.118 mm and 20.711 mm, respectively. It can be seen that the maximum deflection for slab with punching shear reinforcement is slightly higher compared to the Control specimen. Similar trend of finding where slight increment in terms

of maximum deflection for incorporating punching shear reinforcement was also observed in the work of Mabrouk et al. (2017). The insignificant difference in term of deflection at the maximum applied load for specimens with different configuration of punching shear reinforcement can also be seen in the work of Shatarat and Salman (2022). This phenomenon provides an early indication that the use of punching shear reinforcement allows more energy to be absorbed by these specimens in order to resist higher punching shear.

The load-deflection curve can be divided into 3-phases namely linear, non-linear up to maximum punching shear force and a relatively short softening phase before the termination of the test. This observation is particularly true for all cases. The linear phase corresponds to uncracked behaviour of the slab specimen where the load-deflection curves were stiffer before cracks start to develop (Inácio et al., 2015). The non-linear phase corresponds to the deflected slabs with reduced stiffness, and the formation of cracks (Caldentey et al., 2013). The short softening phase correspond to the post peak behaviour. In this case, all specimens show non-plastic behaviour after the post-peak although there is a tendency that all specimens are able to absorb a small amount of energy before collapse. In addition, the load-deflection curve only exhibits a single peak maximum applied load.

(a)

(b)

(c)

(d)

Figure 3 Load-deflection curve for (a) Control specimen (b) Flat Slab 1 (c) Flat Slab 2 and (d) Flat Slab 3

Table 1 shows the ductility ratio calculated for all flat slabs. Based on the results, it can be seen that the introduction of punching shear reinforcement increases the ductility of the flat slab and particularly true for FS1 and FS2. In this case, the ductility ratio was calculated to be 5.749 (FS1) and 5.968 (FS2) compared to 5.620 (Control). However, the ductility ratio of FS3 showed to be the lowest among all the slab specimens. This phenomenon can be associated to the formation of the highest deflection at yield (compared to others) that increases the denominator of the respective equation. In all cases, the ductility ratio of all specimens exceeds 5.0. It is also interesting to note that according to the AS3600-2009 Australian Standard (AS, 2011), structural elements with ductility greater than five (5) behave in a ductile manner and can be used for resisting high loading condition such as earthquake. As such, the introduction of punching shear reinforcement in flat slab has the possibility to be used in earthquake prone and more studies should be conducted in this area.

Table 1 Ductility ratio

Specimen	Deflection at Yield, Δ_y (mm)	Deflection at Peak Load, Δ_u (mm)	Ductility Ratio, (μ_d)	Average Ductility Ratio, (μ_d)
C-1	3.062	18.628	6.084	5.620
C-2	3.167	16.914	5.341	
C-3	3.201	17.403	5.437	
FS1-1	3.656	19.502	5.334	5.749
FS1-2	3.306	19.957	6.037	
FS1-3	3.551	20.866	5.876	
FS2-1	3.295	20.027	6.078	5.968
FS2-2	3.691	19.852	5.378	
FS2-3	3.176	20.475	6.447	
FS3-1	3.936	20.936	5.319	5.034
FS3-2	4.321	20.622	4.773	
FS3-3	4.106	20.574	5.011	

The stiffness of a structure is the degree of a structural element to resist deflection when it is subjected to an applied load (Girish and Lingeshwaran, 2018). The stiffness of the slab specimens is shown in Table 2. The average stiffness of the specimens up to the end of the linear phase was calculated to be 9.614 kN/mm, 12.903 kN/mm, 14.414 kN/mm and 14.342 kN/mm for C, FS1, FS2 and FS3, respectively. The finding also noted the insignificant difference in terms of stiffness between FS2 and FS3. As such, the load-deflection curve of FS2 and FS3 exhibits relatively similar behaviour up to the end of the linear phase. This finding can be due to the fact that both FS2 and FS3 comprises of horizontal, vertical and inclined members in the assembly. Moreover, it is evident that the incorporation of punching shear reinforcement significantly increases the stiffness of the respective slab and particularly true for FS2 and FS3. By setting the result of the Control specimen as the baseline, it can be seen that the increase in the stiffness for using punching shear reinforcement is in the range of 34.21 % to 49.93 %. The increase in the stiffness in the elastic phase for incorporating punching shear reinforcement can also be seen in the work of (Padmanabham and Kumar, 2019).

Table 2 Stiffness for all flat slabs

Specimen	Load at Yield Point, P_y (kN)	Deflection at Yield, Δ_y (mm)	Stiffness, K_s (kN/mm)	Average Stiffness, K_s (kN/mm)
C-1	27.088	3.062	8.847	9.614
C-2	36.963	3.167	11.671	
C-3	26.647	3.201	8.325	
FS1-1	48.294	3.656	13.210	12.903
FS1-2	45.165	3.306	13.662	
FS1-3	42.035	3.551	11.838	
FS2-1	51.028	3.295	15.486	14.414
FS2-2	45.380	3.691	12.295	
FS2-3	49.104	3.176	15.461	
FS3-1	58.169	3.936	14.779	14.342
FS3-2	62.486	4.321	14.461	
FS3-3	56.604	4.106	13.786	

Toughness is also known as the energy absorption and defined as the area under the load-deflection curve (Hason et al., 2021). The average energy absorption of all specimens is shown in Table 3. The average energy absorption for Control, FS1, FS2 and FS3 was calculated to be 1403.82 kN/mm, 1776.07 kN/mm, 2115.95 kN/mm and 2196.59 kN/mm, respectively. It is noted that the introduction of the truss-shaped punching shear reinforcement allows more energy to be absorbed by the flat slab. The percentage increase of the energy absorbed for slabs with punching shear reinforcement was calculated to be in the range of 26.52 % to 56.47 %.

Table 3 Energy absorption for all flat slabs

Specimen	Energy Absorption, (kNmm)	Average Absorption, (kNmm)	Energy Difference, (%)
C-1	1432.774	1403.82	-
C-2	1268.566		
C-3	1510.129		
FS1-1	1762.344	1776.079	26.52
FS1-2	1828.332		
FS1-3	1737.533		
FS2-1	2109.066	2115.95	50.73
FS2-2	1985.887		
FS2-3	2252.890		
FS3-1	2337.769	2196.59	56.47
FS3-2	2188.614		
FS3-3	2063.389		

The ability of FS2 and FS3 to absorb high energy is manifested by the formation of many microcracks before failure as shown in Figure 4 (a) and (b). The absorbed energy is dissipated via the microcracks distributing in the concrete (Hason et al. 2021). As such, the formation of many cracks can be used to indicate the ability of a structural element to absorb energy as a result from the load applied and corresponding deformation (Toader et al., 2018). On the other hand, the formation of microcracks for Control and FS1 was found to be relatively less compared to FS2 and FS3 as shown in Figure 4 (c) and (d). This finding indicates that the absorbed energy was dissipated during the propagation of the microcracks instead of generating more microcracks within the concrete as stated by Słowik (2019).

Figure 4 Crack pattern for (a) Control, (b) FS1, (c) FS2 and (d) FS3 specimen

CONCLUSIONS

Based on the experimental data results, the following conclusion can be drawn:

1. All of the tested flat slab specimens with truss-shaped PSR showed a very similar profile of the load-deflection curve. The graph can be divided into linear, non-linear and short softening phases. Moreover, the insignificant difference in terms of the deflection exhibited by all specimen showed that deflection is not a critical measurement for incorporating truss-shaped punching shear reinforcement.
2. The incorporation of punching shear reinforcement enhanced the punching shear capacity in the order of 7.71 % to 21.47 %. In addition, the incorporation of the truss-shaped punching shear reinforcement also improved the stiffness and ductility of the flat slab specimen.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The authors would like to express their gratitude and appreciation to the Ministry of Higher Education for financing this study and Universiti Sains Malaysia providing the test facilities.

REFERENCES

1. Ahmed, E., Eltaly, B., El-Zhraa, F. and Tayel. M. (2018) Resisting Punching Shear Stress in Reinforced Concrete Slabs. *MATEC Web of Conferences*, **162**.
2. Alwash, N. A. and Al-Mamoori, F. H. N. (2018) Behavior of The RC Slab-Beam System Using Self Compacting Concrete. *International Journal of Engineering & Technology*, **7**, pp. 507-513.
3. Al-Salim, N. H. A., Shwalia, A. S. I. and Al-Baghdadi, H. M. (2021) Enhancement Energy Absorption in Flat Slabs Using Slurry Infiltrated Fibrous Concrete. *IOP Conference Series: Materials Science and Engineering*, **1090**.
4. Bartolac, M., Damjanović, D. and Duvnjak, I. (2015) Punching Strength of Flat Slabs with and without Shear Reinforcement. *Građevinar*, **67**, pp. 771-786.
5. Caldentey, A. P., Patricio, P. L., Hugo, C. P. and Freddy, A. F. (2013) Influence of Stirrup Detailing on Punching Shear Strength of Flat Slabs. *Engineering Structures*, **49**, pp. 855-865.
6. Girish, N. and Lingeshwaran, N. (2018) A Comparative Study of Flat Slabs Using Different Shear Reinforcement Parameters. *International Journal of Engineering & Technology*, **7**, pp. 321-325.
7. Hamdy, M., Saafan, M., Elwan, S. Elzeiny, S. and Abdelrahman, A. (2019) Nonlinear Finite Element Analysis of RC Flat Slabs Strengthened with Steel Shear Bolts. *Al-Azhar University Civil Engineering Research Magazine (CERM)*, **14**.
8. Hason, M. M., Hanoon, A. N., Saleem, S. J., Hejazi, Fa. and Al Zand, A W. (2021) Characteristics of Experimental Ductility Energy Index of Hybrid-CFRP Reinforced Concrete Deep Beams. *SN Applied Sciences*.
9. Husain, M., Eisa, A. S. and Roshdy, R. (2017) Alternatives to Enhance Flat Slab Ductility. *International Journal of Concrete Structures and Materials*, **11**, pp. 161-169.
10. Inácio, M. M. G., Almeida, A. F. O., Faria, D. M. V., Lúcio, V. J. G. and Ramos, A. P. (2015) Punching of High Strength Concrete Flat Slabs without Shear Reinforcement. *Engineering Structures*, **103**, pp. 275-284.
11. Mabrouk, R. T. S., Bakr, M. and Abdalla, H. (2017) Effect of Flexural and Shear Reinforcement on the Punching Behavior of Reinforced Concrete Flat Slabs. *Alexandria Engineering Journal*.
12. Nayef, S., Zaki, W. and Rabie, M. (2019) Effect of Reinforcement on Punching Shear Behavior of Flat Slabs. *International Journal of Civil Engineering and Technology (IJCIET)*, **10**, pp. 2403-2418.
13. Padmanabham, K., and Kumar, K. P. (2019) Punching Shear Improvement of Flat Slabs Using Steel Fibers and Shear Studs. *International Journal of Civil Engineering and Technology (IJCIET)*, **10**, pp. 345-355.
14. Pilakoutas, K. and Li, X. (2003) Alternative Shear Reinforcement for Reinforced Concrete Flat Slabs. *Journal of Structural Engineering, ASCE*, **129**, pp. 1164-1172.
15. Saadoon, A. S., Abbas, A. M. and Hussain, H. K. (2019) A Review on Flat Slab Punching Shear Reinforcement. *Journal of University of Babylon for Engineering Sciences*, **27**, pp. 44-58.
16. Shatarat, N. and Salman, D. (2022) Investigation of Punching Shear Behavior of Flat Slabs with Different Types and Arrangements of Shear Reinforcement. *Case Studies in Construction Materials*, **16**.
17. Slowik, M. (2019) The Analysis of Failure in Concrete and Reinforced Concrete Beams with Different Reinforcement Ratio. *Archive of Applied Mechanics*, **89**, pp. 885-895.
18. Standard A. (2011) Reinforced Concrete Design: In Accordance with AS 3600-2009. *Cement Concrete & Aggregates Australia and Standards Australia*.
19. Toader, T., Haase, W. and Sobek, W. (2018) Energy Absorption in Functionally Graded Concrete Under Compression. *Absorbția De Energie În Betonul Cu Gradient De Densitate Supus La Compresiune*, **64**, pp. 9-23.

